

A RARE CASE OF FIXED-DOSE COMBINATION OF NONSTEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUG INDUCED STEVENS–JOHNSON SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

Stevens–Johnson syndrome (SJS) is a rare but life-threatening mucocutaneous hypersensitivity reaction most commonly triggered by medications. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are frequently implicated because of their widespread use. We report a rare case of SJS following the intake of a fixed-dose combination of Ibuprofen, Paracetamol, and Caffeine in a 38-year-old male. The patient developed erythematous lesions over the back, which progressed to fluid-filled bullae involving the trunk and extremities along with mucosal involvement. Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis. Causality assessment using Naranjo's scale yielded a score of seven, indicating a probable relationship with the suspected drug, while Hartwig's severity scale indicated level four, suggesting moderate severity. The patient was treated with systemic corticosteroids, antibiotics, antiviral therapy, and supportive care, resulting in gradual

improvement. This case highlights the cautious use of over-the-counter fixed-dose combinations.

KEYWORDS: Stevens–Johnson syndrome, NSAIDs, Ibuprofen, adverse drug reaction, pharmacovigilance.

INTRODUCTION

Stevens–Johnson syndrome is a severe mucocutaneous hypersensitivity reaction characterized by epidermal necrosis and detachment involving less than ten percent of the body surface area. It forms part of a spectrum of severe cutaneous adverse reactions that includes toxic epidermal necrolysis. SJS is most triggered by medications (70-90%), infections, idiopathic, malignancy and genetic factors. Drugs frequently associated with SJS include antiepileptics, antibiotics, and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.^[1-3] The mortality and prognosis of patients with SJS can be assessed using the SCORTEN scoring system. The SCORTEN score consists of 7 risk factors: age > 40 years; concomitant malignancy; heart rate > 120 beats/min; epidermal desquamation of >10% of the body surface area at the time of admission; serum urea nitrogen level > 10 mmol/L; serum glucose level > 14 mmol/L and serum bicarbonate level < 20 mmol/L.^[4]

NSAIDs are among the most widely used over-the-counter medications for pain and fever. Fixed-dose combinations containing multiple analgesics are commonly used because of their perceived enhanced therapeutic effect. Among NSAIDS Ibuprofen is more commonly seen causing SJS. Here is a case report of SJS caused by a fixed-dose combination tablet containing ibuprofen 400 mg, paracetamol 325 mg, and caffeine 25 mg.

CASE REPORT

A 38-year-old male had complaints of fever, for which he self-medicated with an over-the-counter preparation, a fixed-dose combination tablet containing ibuprofen 400 mg, paracetamol 325 mg, and caffeine 25 mg. Soon after consumption, the patient developed red, flat lesions over his back associated with pain. Over the next few days, the lesions progressed to fluid-filled vesicles and bullae that spread to involve the abdomen, upper limbs, and lower limbs. The patient also reported a similar episode four years earlier after intake of an unspecified medication.

On examination, vesicles were present over the nape of the neck and forehead, along with erosions at the corner of the mouth and involvement of the nasal mucosa. Pustules were noted in the post-auricular region, and multiple bullae, vesicles, and erosions were observed over the anterior and posterior aspects of the trunk. The pseudo-Nikolsky sign was positive.

Histopathological examination revealed involvement of the epidermis with intraepidermal edema and subepidermal bullae extending into the upper epidermal layers (figure 1). Based on the clinical and histopathological findings, the patient was diagnosed with Stevens–Johnson syndrome. The patient was managed with systemic corticosteroids, antibiotics, other supportive care, and gradual clinical improvement was observed.

Causality assessment using Naranjo’s algorithm yielded a score of seven, indicating a probable association between the adverse reaction and the suspected drug. Severity assessment using Hartwig’s severity scale classified the reaction as level four, suggesting moderate severity.

Figure 1: Patient affected with Steven Johnson syndrome.

DISCUSSION

Stevens–Johnson syndrome is a severe immune-mediated hypersensitivity reaction affecting the skin and mucous membranes. It is most commonly associated with drug exposure, particularly antiepileptics, sulfonamides, antibiotics, and NSAIDs. NSAIDs are among the

most frequently used medications worldwide and are easily available as over-the-counter drugs, which increases the likelihood of adverse reactions.^[1] In the present case, the patient consumed a fixed-dose NSAID combination and developed cutaneous lesions soon after drug intake, along with mucosal involvement. Histopathology confirmed the diagnosis of SJS, and causality assessment demonstrated a probable relationship with the suspected drug.

Fixed-dose combinations may increase the risk of adverse reactions because they contain multiple active ingredients, making it difficult to identify the offending agent and potentially increasing pharmacodynamic interactions.^[5] Early identification of symptoms and immediate withdrawal of the suspected drug are essential to prevent progression to more severe conditions such as toxic epidermal necrolysis.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights a rare but serious adverse drug reaction associated with an over-the-counter fixed-dose NSAID combination. Healthcare professionals and patients should be aware of the risk of severe cutaneous reactions even with commonly used analgesics. Early diagnosis, prompt withdrawal of the offending drug, and appropriate supportive management are crucial for a favorable outcome. Reporting such cases to pharmacovigilance centers is important for improving drug safety data.

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